

FACT SHEET 1: OVERVIEW OF VIVA-PLAN'S MULTI-METHODS RESEARCH

What is VIVA-PLAN?

VIVA PLAN is a dynamic, multi-site research project funded by Formas that aims to investigate sustainability, social inclusion and belonging in residential housing areas of Copenhagen, Denmark, Malmö, Sweden and Södertälje, Sweden. Research outputs will support improvements in green space design and management, and provide policy guidance on sustainable spatial planning across Sweden and Denmark. It is coordinated by the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences in close collaboration with the University of Copenhagen, Södertörn University, Wageningen University, University of Winnipeg and University of Manitoba and a knowledge alliance of policy makers and practitioners ([see details here](#)). The team is composed of planners, geographers and ecologists, and believes in community empowerment as a fundamental research commitment.

What is VIVA-PLAN's approach?

VIVA PLAN uses a **multi-method** research approach, recognising that developing a good understanding of different kinds of knowledge and experiences requires different forms of attention, observation, and analysis. Uniting the different methods is the “Mosaic Governance” approach, which supports the formation of partnerships between local residents and varied cross-sector actors (e.g. state agencies, private firms, etc.). Different aspects of Mosaic Governance are pursued here using four clusters of methods (Figure 1).

* In-between spaces are public and private spheres of planned and unplanned green and grey infrastructure as well as informal and formal, temporary and sustainable, materialised and imagined spaces (Brosius and Schilbach 2016).

Figure 1. An overview of VIVA-PLAN's multi-methods research.

Cluster 1 combines participatory mapping (also known as public participation geographic information systems, or PPGIS) and ethnography to identify issues of social inclusion, safety and security in green spaces and meeting spots in vulnerable residential housing areas, in addition to residents' values and preferences for management of green spaces and meeting spots. The PPGIS focuses on adult residents and ethnography on youth residents. Ecological analysis will also be conducted in order to identify areas

of high biodiversity value. The social values and ecological values will then be linked to identify socially acceptable and ecologically important green spaces and meeting spots for future management.

Cluster 2 combines focus groups and interviews with institutional mapping and photo elicitation to identify social networks of importance to vulnerable residents, and how these networks can be strengthened to address residents' needs. It also considers temporal changes in biodiversity, social inclusion, safety and security in each residential housing area. It builds on insights from WP1 by focusing on the specific needs of vulnerable groups, including youth, elderly, new migrants and longer-term residents.

Cluster 3 builds on work packages 1 and 2 to inform the implementation and evaluation of 'hackathons', which are creative processes that engage government, residents, and corporate and civic organizations in the planning and co-design of green spaces and meeting spots. Here, we will speak with community members, and also planners, geographers, ecologists, and local decision-makers.

Cluster 4 draws together insights from Clusters 1-3 to inform a sustainable spatial planning framework for revitalizing green space and meeting space design in order to improve social inclusion, biodiversity and well-being (including safety and security). Further, in recognition of the importance of promoting social inclusion among diverse groups, we will widen our framework to include the design of 'in-between spaces'. This phase of the project is geared to institutional actors in cities and regional scale departments.

What are the likely benefits for people involved in VIVA-PLAN?

The goal of VIVA PLAN is to empower a broad range of actors concerned with and affected by green design issues. Working at the community level, we hope to generate shared understandings of how nature is conceived and managed in contemporary urban spaces, and how it might be done differently. We specifically hope to equip young people with effective tools for voicing their unique interests, such as through the introduction of sound recording techniques for perceiving nature. For planning authorities and our larger knowledge alliance, we hope to clarify some of the concerns raised by local actors, and to provide concrete steps toward their resolution.

What are the likely outcomes for sustainable spatial planning?

VIVA PLAN will provide detailed, site-specific guidance on how to integrate social issues into the integrated planning and management of green spaces and meeting spots across several residential housing areas in Scandinavia. Our work uses many of the most recognized tools of sustainable spatial planning: public participation geographic information systems (PPGIS), photo and map visualization, ethnography, and detailed policy review. Our study in social network and governance principles, as informed by mosaic governance, will provide planners with a range of materials from which to consider improvements to specific green areas.

Where can I find more information?

Please see our website, www.viva-plan.eu for more information on team members, project design, and supporting literatures. You may also contact the Project Lead (PI):

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